

INTEGRATION OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY WITH HISTORY

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Abstract: Digital history in the broadest sense can be understood as the process of digitizing the past as a result of integrating the field of history with computers, the Internet and other similar modern technologies and, thus, their widespread use in the study, research and re-presentation of history. The practice of digital history, of course, is not limited to digitizing the past.

Keywords: digital history, technologies, research, resources, archives, interactive materials, digital literacy.

Digital history refers to the use of modern computer and communication technologies by historians to digitize archival materials and make them available to users with Internet access. Using technologies ranging from basic web publishing applications to the latest virtual reality (VR) tools, digital historians present historical materials to a diverse audience in new methods and ways and methods.

Digital History does the following:

- * Analyze historical data and create images.
- * Presenting research papers of researchers in an expanded format, informative and interesting;
- * Inviting different audiences to collaborate in creating and telling stories to each other.

Digital History provides links to popular online databases, reviews digital history projects, explains the role of digital historians in academia, and explains what and how a true researcher can prepare for the growing field of modern history.

Historians can use computer technology to collect, analyze, interpret, and present past sources to different audiences. Digital history, in addition to digitizing the past, contributes to the development of scientific research in the field of history and presents the results of scientific research to the public in an interactive mode in a new way. This approach to the study and presentation of historical information is known as digital history.

The integration of primary sources and images with modern technological advances allows historians to turn their research into digitized material. These digital resources are more accessible than traditional methods of presenting research. Digital historians can publish their analysis on websites, blogs, social networks, and online journals.

With digital media tools, digital historians can create dynamic content such as interactive graphs, charts, and maps to help others visualize historical events.

Digital history expands researchers' access to historical sources. Digital History in Schools provides teachers with resources to create more engaging lesson plans and curricula. Digital History also allows you to create digital history projects that will be interesting for different audiences. Digital history resources.

In addition to the traditional methods of book and journal publishing, historians can enrich their research by using information from online platforms that allow interactive data visualization.

Historians can publish their scientific work on open platforms such as Scaral and, Omeka. These platforms, which allow you to collect data from various sources and transform it into visual images, are undoubtedly very useful for historians. Learning about historical data through visualization enriches historical interpretation and teaching, provides additional data context, and facilitates the expression of scientific ideas. Historians have many options for digitizing data. For example, the R programming language is used in digital history projects to create visualizations such as geospatial data, interactive graphics, and animation. Google Books Ngram Viewer allows users to search through millions of digitized books, creating clear graphics.

Digital history resources, such as StoryMaps.ArcGIS, allow you to create descriptive text, images, and multimedia content to present historical information on interactive maps. Historians and teachers can tell stories about events that took place in different places and at different times. An example of this is the Postal Geography website, which covers the opening and closing of post offices in the western United States in the second half of the 19th century.

The Association of American Historians provides digital history resources to help historians implement digital history projects and conduct research. In addition, the digital collections of the Library of Congress and many government digital history projects reflect the variety of materials that can be created using digital history tools.

One of the goals of digital history is to inform a new generation of audiences about important historical information and innovations and involve them in learning about the past. Video and audio podcasts that focus on historical topics and issues can help build online communities. These digital communities allow people to share their shared experiences and interests. Social media is also a handy tool in this process. For example, using the hashtag #twitterstorianson on Twitter can help reach a wider audience of digital projects.

Who is a digital historian?

The theory and methodology of historical science are important for digital history. Digital historians research primary historical sources, such as letters, photographs, archival documents, and more, to write research articles, reports, and presentations. Digital historians verify the authenticity of various written sources, archival documents, and historical materials. They work in state and non-state non-profit organizations, such as museums, libraries, research centers, and various historical associations. The main difference between a digital historian and a regular historian is that when working on historical projects, they conduct research that is integrated with computer technologies.

Conclusion

Digital historians prepare and publish digital materials using digital tools such as infographics, interactive maps, visual images, as well as timelines, charts, and simulations to deliver an inclusive story to a diverse audience.

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